

***Ikouba* Ritual: A Symbol of Cosmology and Worldview of Meitei Community**

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Abstract: Verbal and nonverbal expressive cultural behaviours are the medium to express cosmological ideas through ritual activities. *Ikouba* is a ritual that reflects the Meitei community's values and beliefs about the universe. It involves invoking the deity through specific actions, chanting, singing, and dancing. This ritual uses both man-made and natural materials as a means of accessing the supernatural world and establishing a relationship between ritual and myth. Further, the associated material culture is perceived as a primary source of spiritual power, revealing the foundations of Meitei cosmology. It is a cultural symbol that defines the center of the world, perception, belief systems, and sacred life. So, an ethnographic research has been conducted employing various methods like observation, interviews, focus groups etc. The study of *Ikouba* ritual examines creation and cosmology as a model to understand the beliefs and perceptions of the world through material culture. The physical structures, origin, and evolution of the universe are analyzed as ritual symbolism of the natural-supernatural world. Furthermore, the research aims to examine the dynamic aspects of material culture usage as a means to uncover the thoughts and perceptions of the Meitei community.

Keywords: Cosmology, Cultural behavior, Mythology, Ritual, Symbol.

The cultural expressive behaviors, both verbal and non-verbal, of the Meitei community serve to maintain the stability of their communal ethos. In any community, people are bound together by common interests that connect them within both domestic and public realms. Social solidarity and common identity within a community is demonstrated through shared beliefs, customs, and rituals. This collective consciousness is expressed through material culture, both tangible and intangible, which represents the community's morals, religion, politics, and society. Material culture plays a vital role in connecting the collective psyche through ritual activities, and thus represents the social and cultural identity that distinguishes the group's identity from others (Hales & Hodes, 2010). Like

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other communities, the Meitei people, who live in Manipur¹, express their common identity through the performance of various individual and communal rituals. The origin of Meitei people is still obscure and complicated. The Meitei are an ethnic group in the Manipur valley with a distinct history, language, and ethnicity. They are classified as a mixture of Tibeto-Burman Mongoloid, Australoid, Aryan, and Tai and have developed a strong political and social structure through the absorption of various elements (Kabui, 1991). The Meitei ethnic group was formed through the merging of seven principalities in Manipur. Over time, the Ningthouja principality established dominance and absorbed the other principalities, leading to the term “Meitei” becoming the collective name for all these groups, including several tribes and minor principalities (Sanajaoba, 1988, p.147). So, the political and administrative unit of Meitei was created to construct a common identity, perception, beliefs, and worldview.

This paper focuses on the material culture used in the *Ikouba* ritual, part of the *Umanglai-baraoba*² ritual, to examine the beliefs and cosmology of the Meitei people. The *Umanglai-baraoba* is held to commemorate the creation of the world and to seek prosperity. It involves reenacting creation stories through rituals, dance, and song to appease the deities. Generally, *Umanglai-baraoba* is typically held annually or biannually in every Meitei village during the months of March to July. The date of the event is determined by the elder head of the village, confirmed by the *Maichou Loishang* (a *Pandit* institution that functions as a main office under the palace authority), and may involve input from the *Lai* committee (a group responsible for organizing the ritual).

Many scholars, such as Ngariyanbam Kulachandra (1963), Wahengbam Lukhloi (1989), and Rajkumar Nabindra Singh (2009), have attempted to study the *Umanglai-baraoba* ritual in a systematic and descriptive manner. Their studies reveal the Meitei’s cosmology, civilization, and religion, as they seek to understand their perceptions and conceptions of the world. Wangam Somorjit (2014) has coined the term “Umanglaism” to describe the institutionalized Meitei religious belief system that includes myths, rituals, and the local cults of assimilated and enslaved communities. He also notes that the pantheon of Umanglaism emerged and was assimilated through the process of Meitei territorial expansion. The practices of the *Umanglai-baraoba* ritual have been performed for generations, binding the people into a homogeneous group. However, scholars have not yet conducted academic research on material culture as a primary source of spiritual power, which could reveal the foundations of Meitei cosmology. The tradition of observing the *Umanglai-baraoba* ritual has been passed down through oral narratives, which serve as a living culture and the source of social and cultural stories for understanding the community’s ethos. This paper employs an ethnographic approach, consisting of interviews, focus groups, and observations, to explore the *Ikouba* ritual and its associated cosmology, civilization, and perceptions and conceptions as represented through the material culture and symbolism of the ritual. The aim of the study is to examine the role of material culture as a symbolic representation in shaping reality through ritual practices in the Meitei community. The research will focus on the creation of metaphorical concepts rooted in the physical world and their interplay in the *Ikouba* rituals.

***Ikouba* Ritual Invoking Souls of Deities**

The opening of the *Umanglai-baraoba* ritual is through the *Ikouba* ritual, which is a rite that involves the invocation of the souls of deities from a water body. This ritual is performed by the *Maiba* (priest), *Maibi* (priestess), and *Penakhongba* (a musician who plays the *Pena* instrument), and is followed by the *Thongalloi*³ (participants of the village) after the installation of the images of deities. The *Ikouba* ritual is performed with various acts in different times and contexts, and can be divided into three parts: *Ikumba*, *Itaba*, and *Ikaba/Higaba*.

1. The *Ikumba* ritual, which is a rite of passage, begins at the *Laipung* (courtyard of the temple) and ends at the water body. It is led by the priest, who carries the *Nabeiphu* (a pot for sanctification), and is followed by the priestess, who has a *Sarik* (hand bell), the musician who plays an instrument, a married woman who carries the *Pun Kangnanbi* (a water storing pot), a man holding the *Pe* (parasol), and the *Thongalloi*. The ritual starts with a structured cultural procession in which the *Thongalloi* are arranged in two columns in a sequence, with each participant holding a specific ritual object. The participants' positions and associated materials are given in the following table

Table 1: The position and associated materials with the participants in *Ikumba* ritual

Right side (God Lainingthou Side)	Left side (Goddess Lairemma Side)
<i>Maiba</i> who holds <i>Nabeiphu</i> (pot for sanctification)	
<i>Maibi</i> who holds <i>Sarik</i> (hand bell)	
<i>Penakhongba</i> who play <i>Pena</i> (an instrument)	
A married woman who carries <i>Pun Kangnanbi</i> (pot for carrying water)	
A man holding <i>Pe</i> (Parasol)	A man holding <i>Pe</i> (Parasol)
A man who carries <i>Thang</i> (sword)	A man who carries <i>Thang</i> (sword)
An unmarried woman who carries <i>Kwagok</i> (pan case)	An unmarried woman who carries <i>Kwagok</i> (pan case)
An girl who carries <i>Humai</i> (hand fan)	An girl who carries <i>Humai</i> (hand fan)
An unmarried woman who carries <i>Khudeisel</i> (towel stand)	An unmarried woman who carries <i>Khudeisel</i> (towel stand)
An unmarried woman who carries <i>Kaasel</i> (spittoon)	An unmarried woman who carries <i>Kaasel</i> (spittoon)
A married man who carries <i>Lainingthou Ikouphu</i>	A married man who carries <i>Lairemma Ikouphu</i>
A man who carries <i>Chong</i> (a type of umbrella)	A man who carries <i>Chong</i> (a type of umbrella)
Married woman who holds <i>Lepshum</i> (pounding pestle) and <i>Phida</i> (a cloth for making a seat)	Married woman who holds <i>Lepshum</i> (pounding pestle) and <i>Phida</i> (a cloth for making a seat)
<i>Lai Sellungba</i>	
A married woman who carries <i>Heiruk</i> (fruits) on the <i>Lukmai</i> (a rounded basket)	
A married woman who carries <i>Kheiyom</i> (package of offering items) on <i>Yangkok</i> (winnowing basket)	

2. The *Itaba* ritual is introduced with the *Konyai Hunba* ritual, in which the priest offers two coins—one gold and one silver—to the Mother Goddess Malem Ema. The priest then performs the *Leirai Yu-Khangba* ritual, in which they offer nine bamboo stems full of wine to the nine Laipungthou (male spirits) and seven bamboo stems full of wine to the seven Lainura (female spirits). Next, the priest performs the *Khayom Lakpa* ritual, offering a *Khayom* (a package of ritual items) to the water body. Afterwards, the priestess holds the two *Ikouphu* (pots used for the *Ikouba* ritual) in her hands and performs the *Chuppharon*⁴ ritual dance. She then covers her head with a white cloth, holds a handbell in her left hand and a *Leiyom* (a package of ritual items) in her right hand, and begins chanting in a wailing tone while entering into a trance. She speaks the words of the deities and sings about the creation and the hymn *Leibourol*, accompanied by the *Pena* instrument. During the oracle (*Lai-pao Chenba*⁵), she predicts omens, weather, fortunes, and natural disasters for the village or state. Finally, the souls of the deities are summoned and placed inside the pots in the *Lai Themgatpa* (keeping the deity's souls) ritual.

3. Next, the priest and priestess perform the *Ikaba/Higaba*⁶ ritual, a returning cultural procession that follows the same sequence and positions as the *Thougalloi*. Upon arriving at the gate of the temple, all the participants are welcomed with the incense of *Khoiju Leikham* (*Plectranthus ternifolia* and *Goniothalamus sesquipedalis*) and pass through a flame of fire, and are offered a *Phoudang*⁷ (a basket of paddy offering items), a duck, and a dove. At the temple courtyard, the married woman who carried the *Ishaiphu* (a pot containing sacred water) enters the temple first and places the pot at the abode of the Almighty God Apoka on a piece of banana leaf. The priest and priestess then take out the *Leiyom* attached to the *Hirilang* from the *Ikouphu* of the God and Goddess. Three male participants and the priest hold the thread of Lainingthou, while three female participants and the priestess hold the thread of Lairemma, connecting the respective *Leiyom*. The *Leiyom* is touched at the navel of the God and Goddess images. During this act, the participants ensure that the thread does not fall to the ground or break the pots. Each *Ikouphu* is placed on the respective sides of the God and Goddess. The *Higarol* (disembarking) song is sung during this ritual, which depicts the boat of life in which living souls are carried. After this act, the *Pena* player sings a song to send the deities to sleep, and the priestess performs the *Saroi Khangba* (offerings made to the evil spirits) rites.

Symbolism

Symbols express cultural meaning through rituals, myths, and other expressive forms. Geertz (1973) viewed symbols as elements of culture that communicate and interpret experiences. These symbols shape cultural beliefs and values and inform how people interact with the world. Expressive symbols like religious rituals, myths, and flags are not arbitrary, but have significant meaning for the culture. Understanding the

symbolic meaning of these symbols is key to interpreting a culture. Tilley (1991) stated that material culture symbols are connected to the form and use of everyday and ritual activities, and the meaning of these symbols is linked to the culture's thoughts, cosmologies, cultural concepts, and social structure. In the Meitei community's *Ikouba* ritual, material culture expresses their mystical beliefs through visible representation. The material culture used serves as a physical representation of the community's intangible truth, including beliefs, values, religiosity, and cultural knowledge. These materials are specific to the ritual context and serve a specific purpose. As Gazin-Schwartz (2001) points out, ritual materials are anomalous and do not appear unless they serve a specific ritual purpose. They do not fit into preconceived ideas and always exist within a particular context. The symbolism of the material culture will be explored in five sections: space, costume, water, numbers, and material.

Space

The concept of sacred space⁸, called *Laipung*, is defined not only by the place, but also by the associated materials, whether natural or man-made. According to Apanthoi (2018), space is defined by the material placed within it, reflecting a community's belief system and worldview, and is divided psychologically, not physically. In addition, the sanctification of all participants, who are adorned with appropriate costumes, indicates the separation of social status from their previous position. The prohibition of participants from engaging in sexual relationships, eating leftover food, and wearing unwashed clothing during the prescribed period further separates them from their previous social status and allows them to enter into a liminal⁹ period. The *Ikoupham*, a place for performing the *Ikouba* ritual, is a contextually sacred space located near a water body. The contextualization of space as sacred enables a spatial movement that allows for a change in status.

The spatial passage from *Laibung* to *Ikoupham* involves various stages of the sacred world. During the ritual, the performers - priest, priestess, and instrument players - reenact the myth using appropriate local or regional language and dialects, songs, gestures, and material culture that personify their characters. These ritual activities contextualize a sacred time in which the gods created the Meitei world. According to Eliade (1987, pp. 81-85), the study of cosmogony serves as a paradigmatic model for all creation and the cosmogonic time serves as a model for all sacred times. The sacred time in this culture is when the gods manifested their divinity and created the world. A structured cultural procession, with *Thougalloi* arranged in two columns representing gods and goddesses, is performed in a specific sequence without changing their position or associated ritual objects.

The leading of the ritual, cultural procession, the sanctification of participants and ritual objects, and the opening of the inaugural ritual by the priest indicate the hierarchy of social status and the patriarchal social system of the Meitei community. The Meitei community's patriarchal social system is reflected in the hierarchical arrangement of participants in the *Ikouba* ritual. Men are associated with symbols of power like swords and fans, while women are associated with serving items (see Table 1). This

reflects cultural perceptions of masculinity and femininity and demonstrates gender identity and hierarchy. This structure reveals the level of social structure, including the social system, social categories, status and role, and social hierarchy, which can be considered a social drama¹⁰. The use of handbells and musical instruments in Meitei rituals creates a sacred world through sound and vibration. The materials used to produce these sounds serve as a language between the mundane and sacred worlds and are considered integral to connecting the community with their cosmogony values. Eventually, *Laipung* and *Ikoupham* symbolize the connection between the physical and spiritual world in a cultural worldview. This sacred space holds existential value for the community and is structured through material culture and ritual activities.

Costume

Costumes serve as symbols of communal identity and reveal the social identities within a group. Apanthoi (2018) discusses how the text, texture, and clothing patterns of the Meitei community serve as a way to recognize individual and communal identity. The motifs, which originated from Lord Pakhangba, played a significant role in unifying the community under a common belief system. In the community, costumes reveal social and cultural identity based on gender, age, and status, divided into three categories: the costume of the ritual observer, the costume of the person carrying the deity, and the costume of *Thongaloi*.

The costume of the ritual observer includes the attire worn by priests, priestesses, and *Pena* players. There are two types of dress for priests and *Pena* players based on their status and role within their social and cultural norms. Newcomers in these professions typically wear a plain white dhoti without a border design, a long-sleeve shirt, a *Salai Kokeyet* (turban) with a *Changkebrang Tabi* motif, and a white *Innaphi* (shawl) hanging from their neck. Priests and *Pena* players who have been recognized by the state, on the other hand, wear a dhoti with a *Khamen Chatpa* motif, a velvet shirt, a turban with a *Namthang Khuthat* motif, bangles, and armbands. There are also two types of dresses for priestesses based on their status. Newcomers in this profession typically wear a plain white sarong, a white long-sleeve shirt, and a white shawl wrapped around the waist. Priestesses who have been recognized by the state, on the other hand, wear a white *Phanek*¹¹ (Sarong), a velvet shirt, a sarong cloth, bangles, and armbands.

The costume of the person who carries the deity consists of a white and plain dhoti, a white long-sleeve shirt, a white *Salai Kokeyet* (turban) with a *Changkebrang Tabi* motif, and a white *Innaphee* (shawl). The body is wrapped in a shawl that covers the whole body and is tied at the neck with the two ends of the cloth. The clothing patterns worn by this person serve to differentiate their role and position within the community.

In the Meitei community, the costumes of *Thongaloi* worn by male participants consist of a white turban, white dhoti, white long-sleeve shirt, and white shawl. Female participants wear a *Mayek Naibi Phanek* (sarong) and a white shawl. White color represents the religious life of Meitei community and connection between the god's world and the living world. It symbolizes purity and dedication to the gods. Priests, priestesses, and *Pena* players connect the two worlds through rituals, shaping cultural identity. Cultural

identity is shaped by the context in which a symbol is enacted and how it is perceived and behaviors by community members (Pratt & Rafaeli, 1997, p. 863). Therefore, the costume of each participant signifies sacredness, purity, status, and gender identity.

Water

In the Meitei community, water bodies are believed to be the home of spirits and are seen as divine, representing the origin of life. Water is considered the origin of the communal ideology that shapes the cultural belief system of the community (Das, 2018, p.110). In the *Ikouba* ritual, water is a primary source for the conception of divinities and the cosmos in Meitei religion. In the *Konyai Hunba*, *Khayom Lakpa*, and *Lai Themgatpa* rituals, water¹² is used as a medium in which various practices connect humanity and divinity, bridge paradoxes, transcend different human and divine realms, allow interactions with gods, and enable divinities to interfere with humanity. It is believed that the almighty god Guru Sidaba created living creatures while he was in or on water, and that before the creation of the living world, there was nothing. In this context, water represents the void, the abstract space where life originated. Eliade (1987, p.130) states that water symbolizes all possibilities of existence and shapes the religious values of symbols. The *Ikouba* ritual prohibits villagers from fetching water, as it is believed to bring harm, creating the idea of the sacredness of water in contrast to the profane world.

Numbers

In the Meitei community, numbers such as two, three, four, five, nine, etc. are used as symbols in various contexts in rituals. Dundes (1980, pp.134-159) notes that studies of numbers in American culture reveal important elements of culture. No number is universal for a cultural group, as pattern numbers vary based on culture. Cultural patterns in social organization and religion often manifest in language and time. Conversely, patterns found in language and time can also be indicative of cultural patterns in social organization and religion. In the *Konyai Hunba* ritual, the two coins symbolize *Pa* (man/father) and *Pi* (woman/mother) and are used to show veneration and summon the god and goddess for the coronation. The two white and red coins represent male and female, respectively. Offering beverages is performed to avoid disrupting the ritual activities. In the *Ikouba* ritual, the two *Ikouphu* and two *Khayom* represent the right side as God Lainingthou and the left side as Goddess Lairemma.

Material

In the Meitei community, the materials used in rituals can be classified into two types: natural and man-made. Ames (1985, pp.3-5) notes that natural and man-made materials are both created from human ideas and concepts of value and utility, developed over time through use and experimentation. Both natural and man-made materials are used to represent Meitei social and cultural phenomena, traditional knowledge, and relationships.

Khayom

Khayom is a traditional ritual object that is created through a structured process involving the arrangement of specific items, including rice grains, a fresh egg containing two coins, and three buds of *Langthrei* (Burma Agrimony). These items are wrapped in seven or three layers of banana leaves, which are placed on the ground with the leaves facing upward for the goddess *Lairemma* and facing downward for the god *Lainingthou*. The fresh egg is placed on top of the heap of rice grains and the buds of *Langthrei* are inserted into the hole on its top. The banana leaves are then tied together using *Utang Paya* (bamboo strips), with the number of strips differing according to whether the *Khayom* is being made for *Lainingthou* (nine strips) or *Lairemma* (seven strips). In Meitei culture, an egg in the *Khayom* package symbolizes the almighty god, and two coins symbolize the souls of the god and goddess, believed to have originated from the almighty god. The three buds of *Langthrei* (Burma Agrimony) are associated with the triad deities of *Leishemba* (creator), *Leingakpa* (protector), and *Leitakpa* (destroyer), and are seen as providing evidence of mythology and confirming the sacred concept of the trinity and the notion of three-in-one in Meitei religion and culture. In this culture, the passage of time is understood as being divided into past, present, and future, and the three layers of banana leaves are believed to represent the involvement of these time periods in the life cycle. The heap of rice grains symbolizes the countless living creatures created by the almighty god, with each grain representing the wealth and abundance found in the lap of Mother Earth. The package of items is bound together with *Paya* (finely knifed thin bamboo strips), which signifies the force that binds everything together under the vision of the almighty god. This binding is also thought to represent the existence of the almighty god on the water before he created the celestial bodies. The act of casting two *Khayom* packages into the water is believed to symbolize the copulation needed to create everything in the world. According to Somorjit (2013), the present ritual of offering *Khayom* package is believed to have originated from the shooting-sun myth of the Meitei community, which represents the natural cycle of celestial bodies. The offering package of banana leaves containing a fresh egg is used to summon the sun in this ritual. In general, the *Khayom* and its ritual activities are understood to symbolize the cosmology of the Meitei culture, in which the physical structure of the world is connected to their metaphysical beliefs.

Ikouphu

Ikouphu is a small earthen pot that is easy to carry and hold. It does not have a specific design or purpose, but becomes an *Ikouphu* when it is decorated with banana leaves and a prepared *Leiyom* (ritual package) is placed inside and bound with *Hirilang* (sacred nine-strand thread) around its neck. The *Leiyom* (ritual package) of the god *Laiyingthou* consists of three layers of banana leaves facing downward and fourteen buds of *Langthrei* (Burma Agrimony), which are bound with nine strands of thread. Of these fourteen buds, five are offered to the Guru, and nine are offered to nine male deities. The *Leiyom* (ritual package) of the goddess *Lairemma* consists of three layers of banana leaves facing upward and seven buds of *Langthrei*, which are bound with seven

strands of thread. This information is specific to the cultural context in which *Ikouphu* and *Leiyom* are used. In the cultural context being described, two *Ikouphu* pots are used in a ritual dance performed by the priestess. One *Ikouphu* is designated for the god and the other for the goddess, and they are held by the priestess while performing the dance. A white cloth covering the priestess's head and mouth signifies another stage of the ritual. This dance is believed to have been inspired by a mythical event in the community and is meant to recall the creation of living beings on Earth. The dance is seen as a way of paying homage to the directional deities, who are believed to protect the Earth. The two *Ikouphu* pots are also thought to represent the sky (*Leithak*) and the Earth (*Leikha*), and the ritual is known as *Leithak Leikha Lakpa* (dipping the sky and Earth into the water). The placement of the pots and the materials contained within them differ according to their designated direction. In the described cultural context, the sound produced by the bell and the beating of the *Leiyom*, which are connected to the *Ikouphu* through *Hirilang* (thread), create a unique environment within the sacred world when they are struck on the surface of the water by the priestess. The chant, the sound of the *Pena* (a musical instrument), the rippling of the water, and the vibration of the threads are thought to create a threshold that allows the priestess to enter the supernatural world. Keeping the *Leiyoms* inside the *Ikouphu* is seen as summoning the souls of the deities and keeping them alive within the pot. This act of summoning and keeping the souls inside the pot is symbolically associated with pregnancy. On the other hand, the *Punkangnanbi* or *Irangpun* (pot) becomes *Ishaiphu*, representing the Mother Goddess, when it is filled with water. Symbolically, touching the respective *Leiyoms* at the navel part of the images of the deities is believed to represent the resurrection of their souls. The proper arrangement of materials in specific places is thought to indicate the power of the materials and the spatial structure of the ritual. The act and song of *Higaba* are believed to signify the concept of a boat of life and the existence of the god and goddess with the people.

The Meitei culture believes that material culture influences reality through rituals and creates symbolic ideas based on physical experiences. They use material culture to express the supernatural, embodied in the *Laipung* and *Ikoupham*. Material culture among the Meitei provides insight into their worldview and impacts their cognitive experience more than language. It is used as a symbolic representation of their cultural experiences and has significance in their religion, reflecting their beliefs about the supernatural world and influencing their behavior. The material culture in Meitei religion holds symbolic meanings and facilitates belief in the supernatural world. It is a source of power and authority due to its connections to sacrality and mythology. Rituals using these materials reflect the community's cosmology and carry symbolic values, with specific functions and structures associated with the context of the rite. The *Ikouba* ritual in Meitei culture reflects beliefs about cosmogony, divinity, and creation through the use of material culture, chant, dance, and song. It also reflects the societal structure and gender identity of the community, with a hierarchical arrangement of participants and associated materials. Concepts of purity, pollution, and sanctification are demonstrated through

space separation, indicating the participant's status within the community. The ritual also displays cultural perceptions of masculinity and femininity through its elements.

Every object of material culture is used in a specific way that signifies the context of the ritual, and the materials have relationships with one another as the ritual progresses. Material culture serves as a language to communicate the mundane and sacred worlds of the Meitei, signifying the context of the *Ikouba* ritual, with the materials having relationships with one another as the ritual progresses. In Meitei religious life, the dominant use of white in costumes symbolizes the sacred and represents purity and dedication to the gods. The meaning and significance of colors can vary based on time and place and reveal deeper cultural meanings reflecting the community's perceptions and worldview. Water is seen as a medium linking the human and divine realms, demonstrated in rituals through the perception of water as divine and a source of existence. Significant numbers (e.g. one, two, three, five, seven, nine) have specific meanings in Meitei folklore, and ritual activities incorporating numbers, directions, place changes, and material objects reflect the community's perceptions and worldview. The rituals reenact creation stories, honoring deities to receive their protection and care, symbolizing the transformation from mundane to supernatural world. The *Laijung*, where spirits and deities are present, represents the community's worldview and belief system intertwined with cultural products, forming a comprehensive text identifying their ethnic group.

Material culture is a central aspect of Meitei culture, playing a significant role in the creation and expression of collective identity and worldview. As a heterogeneous group with various cultural influences, the Meitei people use material culture to express and reinforce their common identity through ritual. The communal ritual of *Umanglai-haraoba* serves as an epistemological framework for understanding Meitei beliefs, attitudes, and knowledge systems, while the *Ikouba* ritual reveals the structure of Meitei society, gender roles, and perceptions of the natural world. Material culture is closely tied to Meitei spiritual beliefs and practices, and is often seen as a means of connecting with the supernatural world through symbolic transformative processes. The use of specific materials in rituals and other cultural practices is believed to lend transformative power and to serve as a threshold between the spiritual and physical realms. The space observed by the community possesses existential value and becomes the center of the world, which is equivalent to the creation of a world that shows cosmogonic value. The form and matter of perception take place through material culture. There is a relation between ideas and practices and the material cultures created or modified by Meitei people. The use of material culture in Meitei ritual activities connects physical phenomena to beliefs, moral values, and religion. The material culture contextualizes sacred time and space, serving as a threshold to connect with the spiritual world. Efficacious materials, songs, and chants associated with rituals bring about symbolic transformative processes in Meitei's supernatural world. Metaphorical embodiment in Meitei material culture is a temporal aspect that is conceptualized to make sense of experience. The Meitei worldview, cosmology, and belief system are closely intertwined with material culture, forming a comprehensive text that identifies the ethnic group.

Notes

1 Manipur is a state in NE India, bordering Myanmar, with a mountainous region and a valley inhabited by the Meitei people. It was named by Garibniwaz and made Vaishnavism the state religion. Previously called “Mekhala,” it has a long history of political organization and strong kingdoms. See Naorem Sanajaoba (Ed.) (1988), *Manipur, Past and Present: The Heritage and Ordeals of a Civilization* (Vol. 4), pp. 3-9. New Delhi: Mittal Publications.

2 *Umanglai-baraoba*, a Meitei communal ritual, is believed to have been introduced by Soraren. Deities of *Umanglai-baraoba* can exist in various forms, including as ancestors or guardian spirits, and some are believed to have lived as humans in the past (e.g. Pakhangba, Poreiton, Nongpok Ningthou).

3 *Thougallois* are married individuals with an elder son who follow specific rituals, including eating leftover rice, wearing impure clothing, and engaging in sexual activity, for a specified period.

4 Leishemba dance portrays creation myth of Goddess Nongthang Leima and is performed to appease directional guardians and water deities in the direction of Thangjing (southwest), Marjing (northeast), Wangbren (southeast), and Koubru (northwest). The dance is believed to control Haraba and God Ashiba create creatures.

5 Literally, the term refers to a message or information that is revealed or delivered by gods and goddesses.

6 Through dance, the priestess performs three stages of receiving the deities: forming a bubble, initiating small water lettuce, and growing the water lettuce to a larger size.

7 An offering item made of one basketful of paddy, a string of small fish, a pair of salt dishes, and a metal object placed above the surface.

8 Sacred space as having structure and consistency that is opposite to that of profane space, with a formless expanse surrounding it. See Mircea Eliade (1987), *The Sacred and the Profane: The Nature of Religion*, pp. 21-22. New York: A Harvest Book, Harcourt, Inc.

9 Model for analyzing a ritual process consists of three major phases: rites of separation, transition, and incorporation. See Arnold van Gennep (1960), *The Rites of Passage*. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.

10 Social drama reveals the relationship among actors (kinship, position, class, status) and their bonds/oppositions of interest and friendship, network, and informal relationship. See Victor Turner (1982), *From Ritual to Theatre: The Human Seriousness of Play*, p.12. New York: Paj Publications.

11 The Meitei distinguish secular and sacred aspects through the use of *Phanek*. Women wear *Pumngou Phanek* in daily life, except white, light pink or off-white, which are used for ritual purposes. Priestesses wear white *Phanek*, while others wear light pink or off-white with border stripes, symbolizing purity, devotion, and spirituality. Wearing *Phanek* in rituals and prayers connects the wearer to the sacred world from their secular life. See Apanthoi (2022), “Textiles as a Cultural Symbols: A Study through the *Phanek* of Meitei Community”, *Antrocom Journal of Anthropology*, 18 (2b), p.615.

12 Oestigaard explains that water is key to ancient religious practices, offering insight into religion, the divine, and rituals. Water connects humans and the divine and facilitates communication with deities, unites microcosm and macrocosm, brings life, and legitimizes social hierarchies and religious practices. Water bridges human and divine worlds, enabling divine intervention. See Timothy Insoll (Ed.) (2011), *The Oxford Handbook of the Archaeology of Ritual and Religion*, p.38. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.

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